

D3.1

Protocol to assess land degradation

Date: 11.11.2024

Version: 2.1

**Funded by
the European Union**

SOIL O-LIVE (Grant Agreement ID: 101091255) is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EIC. Neither the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

D3.1 Protocol to assess land degradation

Document Information

Project title	SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES
Project acronym	SOIL O-LIVE
Grant Agreement	101091255
Work package	WP3 Soil erosion and land degradation
Deliverable number and title	D3.1 Protocol to assess land degradation
Deliverable description	A protocol to assess soil and land degradation at farm and landscape level
Deliverable type	R — Document, report
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Lead beneficiary	UNIROMA3
Due submission date	30 June 2024 (M18)
Submission date	25.04.25

Document Author(s) and Reviewer(s)

Name	Entity	Role (author, reviewer)
P. Borrelli	UNIROMA3	Author/Reviewer
C. Alewell	UB (Univ. Basel)	Author/Reviewer
K. Kaffas	UNIROMA3	Author/Reviewer
P. Saggau	UNIROMA3	Author/Reviewer
F. Matthews	UNIROMA3	Author/Reviewer

Document history

Version	Date	Made by	Short Description of Changes
1.1	30.06.2024	Borrelli P. (IT), Alewell C. (CH), Kaffas K. (IT), Saggau P. (IT), Matthews F. (IT)	Initial version
2.1	11.11.2024	Borrelli P. (IT), Alewell C. (CH), Kaffas K. (IT), Saggau P. (IT), Matthews F. (IT)	Updated version after RP1 comments of evaluators

Table of Contents

Document Information.....	2
Table of Contents	3
List of Tables	4
List of Figures	4
List of Acronyms and abbreviations	4
Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Land Degradation: Some definitions	6
3. Context for method development	7
4. A protocol to assess soil and land degradation at farm level	10
4.1. Summary and scope	10
4.2 Methodology	11
4.2.1. Cumulative soil erosion rates [CSE]	12
4.2.2. Farmable land loss due to gully and badlands [G&B]	13
4.2.3. Soil organic matter loss [SOM]	13
4.2.4. Status of ground vegetation [SGV]	13
4.2.5. Soil salinity [SSa]	14
4.2.6. Soil acidification [SAC]	14
4.2.7. Soil compaction [SCo].....	15
4.2.8. Phosphorus deficiency [PDf]	15
4.2.9. Soil pollution from heavy metals [SHM]	15
4.2.10. Soil moisture [SMo]	16
4.3 Example of the Land Multidegradation Index <i>LMIdebt</i>	16
4.4 Future testing sites	17
5. Conclusions	19
References	20

List of Tables

Table 1. The LD indicators considered for assessing the land multi-degradation in olive orchards.

Table 2. Cumulative erosion rates of water, wind, tillage, and harvest erosion.

Table 3. Area interested by gully erosion and badlands.

Table 4. Soil Organic Carbon.

Table 5. Ground vegetation cover.

Table 6. Soil salinization scores.

Table 7. Soil acidification.

Table 8. Degree of soil compaction.

Table 9. Soil nutrient imbalances.

Table 10. Limit concentrations of heavy metals in topsoil.

Table 11. Total amount of water in soil.

Table 12. Olive orchard plots with size (ha) and type of management (DH, ORG, and TD).

List of Figures

Figure 1. The dependency wheel from EUSO between pairs of soil degradation processes.

Figure 2. Spatial pattern of the land multi-degradation in the European orchards by NUTS2.

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of the *LMIdebt* calculation for a hypothetical Soil District.

Figure 4. Example of *LMIdebt* computation for two target sites in Spain (left) and Italy (right).

Figure 5. Spatial distribution of the SOIL O-LIVE orchard plots across the Mediterranean region.

List of acronyms and abbreviations

ELD	Economics of Land Degradation Initiative
JRC	European Commission's Joint Research Centre
EEA	European Environment Agency
EU	European Union
EUSO	European Union Soil Observatory
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GLASOD	Global Assessment of Soil Degradation
LD	Land degradation
LMI	Land Multi-degradation Index
SD	Soil Degradation
SOM	Soil Organic Matter
UNCCD	United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme

Executive Summary

Land degradation is a major challenge, threatening agricultural productivity, food security, and environmental sustainability. Olive groves, in particular, face significant risks from soil erosion, pollution, and nutrient imbalances.

To address this issue, the report introduces a standardized protocol for assessing soil and land degradation at both the farm and landscape levels, enabling comparisons across different Mediterranean regions. A modified Land Multidegradation Index (LMI) is proposed as a tool to quantify degradation at the farm level. This approach moves beyond the traditional focus on individual degradation factors and instead considers multiple interconnected degradation pathways.

The methodology is based on a multi-indicator scoring system inspired by the EU Soil Observatory's convergence of evidence approach. It identifies ten key indicators of soil degradation, including soil erosion, organic matter loss, pollution from heavy metals and pesticides, nutrient imbalances, and vegetation degradation. The protocol employs a benchmarking system that compares the condition of olive orchards against semi-natural reference sites within similar soil and climatic conditions, allowing for a relative assessment of land degradation.

Implementation of this protocol will be tested across 53 study sites in Greece, Italy, Morocco, Portugal, and Spain. The goal is to contribute to future EU soil monitoring efforts and inform policy development for soil restoration and certification of healthy soils. The results from this study will also provide critical insights into effective soil restoration techniques and sustainable olive oil production.

In conclusion, the proposed protocol marks a significant advancement in harmonized soil health monitoring within Mediterranean olive orchards. By offering a comprehensive and scalable framework for assessing soil degradation, it has the potential to support sustainable land management, influence policy decisions, and enhance agricultural resilience in response to climate change.

1. Introduction

SOIL O-LIVE - *The soil biodiversity and functionality of mediterranean olive groves*, is a project funded by the EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe, Under Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, aimed at assessing the environmental condition of olive grove soils on a large scale in the major Mediterranean olive production areas. SOIL O-LIVE has several aims: 1) examine how pollution and land degradation affect olive groves' soils, 2) investigate the connection between soil health and the quality and safety of olive oil, 3) implement effective soil amendments and ecological restoration practices, and 4) establish strict ecological thresholds for healthy European olive groves.

The overall objective of Work Package 3 "*Soil erosion and land degradation*" of the SOIL O-LIVE project is the design and development of a harmonized framework to monitor and assess the state of soil and land degradation due to erosion under cultivation of olive trees in line with the objectives of the EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe.

The present deliverable constitutes the first outcome of Work Package 3 and outlines a protocol for conducting standardized and harmonized soil degradation mapping and monitoring at farm and landscape level in olive orchards. This enables the intercomparison among the different SOIL O-LIVE sites distributed across the Mediterranean region under different pedoclimatic and management conditions. This deliverable is a contribution to the achievement of the SOIL O-LIVE's (scientific) Expected Impact 1, "*Multidisciplinary and field-specific - Increase in scientific knowledge*".

2. Land Degradation: Some definitions

Land, with its defining elements of soils, vegetation, and inland water resources (UNCCD, 2017), is under threat globally from a variety of degradation processes (Právělie, 2021) that can lead to a decrease or collapse of biological and economic productivity, biodiversity, ecological integrity and complexity, or ecosystem functions that support the delivery of primary ecosystem services (Cherlet, Hutchinson, Reynolds et al. 2018; Montanarella, Scholes, Brainich et al. 2018). Land degradation (LD) has profound negative implications for agricultural productivity (Barbier and Hochard, 2018), food security (Právělie, 2021), climate stability (Olsson et al. 2019), environmental sustainability (Borrelli, Panagos, Alewell et al. 2023), and economic prosperity (UNCCD, 2017). For the last case alone, it is predicted that the global economic effect of LD, as measured by the destruction of multiple ecosystems, is \$6.3–10.6 trillion annually (ELD Initiative, 2015; UNCCD, 2017).

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 1999) of the United Nations, LD can be defined as "*the reduction in the capability of the land to produce benefits from a particular land use under a specified form of land management*". This reduction in capability can be caused by multiple interconnected factors that lead to land degradation, with the most significant being (FAO, 1999):

- *Soil degradation*: Decline in the productive capacity of the soil as a result of soil erosion and changes in the hydrological, biological, chemical and physical properties of the soil.

- *Vegetation degradation*: Decline in the quantity and/or quality of the natural biomass and decrease in the vegetative ground cover.
- *Water degradation*: Decline in the quantity and/or quality of both surface and ground water resources.
- *Climate deterioration*: Changes in the micro- and macro-climatic conditions that increase the risk of crop failure.
- *Losses to urban/industrial development*: Decline in the total area of land used, or with potential, for agricultural production as a result of arable land being converted to urban, industrial and infrastructure uses.

In the context of agricultural environments such as olive orchards soil degradation (SD) certainly assumes a predominant role. A joint FAO, UNEP and UNESCO study (FAO, 1979) defined soil degradation as “*a process which lowers the current and/or the potential capability of the soil to produce (quantitatively and/or qualitatively) goods or services*”. In this early attempt, six categories of soil degradation processes were identified: (i) water erosion, (ii) wind erosion, (iii) waterlogging and excess of salts, (iv) chemical degradation, (v) physical degradation, and (vi) biological degradation.

According to the European Environment Agency (EEA, 2000), the main degradation problems of the EU soils are the irreversible losses due to increased soil sealing and erosion, as well as ongoing deterioration caused by local and diffuse contamination (acidification and heavy metals). In its latest report the European Environment Agency (EEA, 2020) states that soil degradation is not well monitored in the European Union; it is often hidden, but it is also widespread and diverse.

3. Context for method development

While the conceptualization of LD and its sub-processes is not a complex exercise per se, mapping and spatially classifying areas affected by different degrees of LD is a much harder task. The lack of reliable large-scale data forces both policy makers and scientific communities to resort to pioneering studies carried out during the late 1980s and early 1990s such as the UNEP’s project “Global Assessment of Soil Degradation” (GLASOD, Oldeman, 1994). GLASOD provided insights based on a static observation approach but did not quantify the effects driven by changes in land use. LD is primarily driven by modifications in land use and management. Spatial patterns of land use and land cover change, especially in areas susceptible to LD, provide further reasons to re-evaluate former qualitative approaches, considering the worldwide increase of cropland and grasslands by more than 280 million hectares (ca. 20%) between 1985 and 2020.

In 2023, the European Union (EU) Soil Observatory (EUSO) – European Commission’s Joint Research Centre (JRC) – launched the Soil Health Dashboard, with the aim to spatiotemporally defining the proportion of EU land affected by soil degradation. The latest version of the Soil Health Dashboard indicates that approximately 63% of the soils of the EU are in an unhealthy state and are subjected to one or more forms of physical or chemical degradation. This is according to the so-called ‘convergence of evidence’ approach (Panagos, Borrelli, Jones et al. 2024), which considered indicators of 16 individual soil degradation processes and their possible interconnections and dependencies (Fig. 1). Despite not yet mature enough, the EUSO’s

approach, strongly relying on the EU land use and land cover survey (LUCAS), aspiring to become a spatiotemporal assessment in the future (De Rosa et al., 2024).

Figure 1. The dependency wheel from EUSO showing the extent of the overlapping area between the pairs of soil degradation processes (Image source: EUSO Dashboard). Left to right: Combination of soil carbon stock, soil compaction, soil salinization, and soil biodiversity with other soil degradation indicators listed.

Subsequent to the launch of the EUSO’s dashboard, Právělie, Borrelli, Panagos et al. (2024), within the framework of the projects EUroLand (funded by NextGenerationEU PNRR Romania) and AI4SoilHealth (funded by Swiss SERI under the grant agreement no. 101086179), proposed a unifying modelling scheme of multiple soil degradation pathways in Europe. Právělie, Borrelli, Panagos et al. (2024) looked at twelve processes that the authors identified as most relevant for highlighting the degradation of agricultural landscapes in Europe (and worldwide), considering certain bio-physical mechanisms, general or specific, which trigger various negative effects in land productivity (processes: Water erosion, wind erosion, soil organic carbon loss, soil salinization, soil acidification, soil compaction, soil nutrient imbalances, soil pollution from pesticides, soil pollution from heavy metals, vegetation degradation, groundwater decline, and aridity). Their findings revealed that soil pollution from pesticides has, surprisingly, the largest spatial footprint at continental level (52% of the cumulated agricultural area of the 40 investigated countries, or ~1.10 million (M) km²), of all analysed processes (Fig. 1). This process has a vast spatial extent due to the very large number of relevant substances (dozens of herbicides, insecticides, and fungicides) considered in the modelled data of pesticide risk. Following soil pollution by pesticides is the degradation due to soil nutrient imbalances (39% or ~0.82 M km²), soil pollution from heavy metals (31%, ~0.60 M km²), and aridity (26%, ~0.54 M km²) (Fig. 1). These four LD processes can be considered the most important in terms of spatial footprint, keeping in mind that each affect over a quarter of European agriculture.

Focusing on olive orchards, after running a data analysis, we confirm that soil pollution from pesticides has the largest spatial footprint (86%, ~3.7 M ha), followed by aridity (80%, 3.4 M ha), water erosion (42%, 1.8 M ha), and soil pollution from heavy metals (37%, 1.5 M ha). Observing the results of the Land Multi-degradation Index (LMI) proposed by Právělie, Borrelli, Panagos et al. (2024) by fusing the twelve geospatial databases, we found between one and eight co-occurring processes in the European Union olive orchards, which were grouped into five degradation classes (the "No degradation" class was approached separately, as it entails the absence of degradation conditions) – very low (1 LD process identified at pixel level, 7% of the

area), low (2 LD processes, 28%), medium (3 LD processes, 44%), high (4 LD processes, 14%) and very high (≥ 5 LD processes, 5%) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Spatial pattern of the land multi-degradation index (LMI) in the European orchards averaged by NUTS2.

4 A protocol to assess soil and land degradation at farm level

4.1 Summary and scope

With the D3.1 report we propose an ad hoc modified version of the Land Multidegradation Index (LMI) introduced by Právělie, Borrelli, Panagos et al. (2024) that uses the principle of multiple land degradation pathways to objectively quantify the degree of LD at the farm-level for olive orchards. Such an approach allows us to avoid dealing with LD from a unilateral perspective, wherein each individual activity is considered as a separate, disconnected pathway within a larger set of processes which typically interact to form the complete LD mechanism. Furthermore, the proposed approach would not a priori limit future landscape, regional or even pan-Mediterranean upscaling potential; like in the case of the Soil Health Evaluation, Rating Protocol and Assessment (SHERPA) scheme (Alewell et al. in progress) targeting all EU land uses.

In addition, it is worth highlighting that the proposed methodology, for assessing LD in olive orchards, primarily targetes SD processes, which tend to induce a decline in the productive capacity of the soil as a result of soil erosion and changes in the hydrological, biological, chemical and physical properties of the soil (FAO, 1999). Tough subordinate with respect to SD, vegetation degradation aspects are also considered. The same is true for FAO's (1999) 'losses to urban/industrial development', which we converted into 'losses of agricultural utilisable land',

understood as a decline in the total area of land used, or with potential, for agricultural production as a result of extreme land degradation processes such as deep gully erosion and badlands.

4.2 Methodology

To design a methodology able to assess land multi-degradation objectively and comprehensively in the Mediterranean olive orchards, we followed the principle of ‘convergence of evidence’ proposed by the EU Soil Observatory (EUSO) (Panagos, Borrelli, Jones et al. 2024) and subsequently refined by Právělie, Borrelli, Panagos et al. (2024). Accordingly, we considered that certain bio-physical mechanisms which cause varied detrimental effects on land productivity can be used as pertinent indicators for degradation of agricultural landscapes. In our approach, however, we attempted to move a step further compared to the previous approaches by:

- i. Surpassing the binary scheme of the two previous approaches (based on single thresholds), returning to a multiple scoring system for each concurrent LD process (or indicator) as recently suggested in the SHERPA scheme.
- ii. Introducing a reference for each selected concurrent LD indicator based on an average value defined by observing ‘semi-natural reference’ sites (grasslands) in the proximity of the target olive orchard. The reference sites are an expression of land that, though still under the historic influence of human activities, on average, tend to represent more semi-natural and therefore healthier soil conditions. The semi-natural reference is spatially delineated following the concept of soil districts, understood as areas having similar geopedological and climate condition. Land conditions and soil analytics to define the reference values for each LD indicators in a given soil district, can be acquired using field observations, earth observation data and LUCAS topsoil (Panagos, Van Liedekerke, Borrelli et al., 2022a), or alternatively, for what concerns the soil analytics, when applicable, this information can be extracted from national or ad hoc soil sampling campaigns.

The ‘semi-natural reference’ for each concurrent LD process (or indicator) is defined, at soil district level (average value of n observations), ranked using a scoring system based on integer numbering from 0 to 3 (see tables below). In the following step, all the scores estimated for the considered n indicators are summarized to define the ‘semi-natural reference’ Land Multidegradation Index reference (LMI_{base}) for a given soil district, spatially defined according to its similar geopedological and climate condition. Based on a n number of LD indicators, here considered, the LMI_{base} may range from a minimum value of 0 (healthy soil) to a maximum value of 30 (very unhealthy soil). Finally, the LMI_{base} value is related through arithmetic difference to the ones defined in each target olive orchard (LMI_{target}) located within the same soil district. The delta between each pair of indicator’s values represents the LMI_{debt} of each target olive orchard (Eq.1; Fig. 3):

$$LMI_{debt} = \sum_{n=1}^{10} LD_{Reference} - \sum_{n=1}^{10} LD_{Target\ orchard}$$

[Eq.1]

The concept of LD ‘debt’ was introduced by Wuepper, Borrelli, Panagos et al. (2021), where each indicator is defined as the difference between current conditions and what it would be under native conditions, without anthropogenic land use, which is interpreted as our global ‘debt’ in each dimension. As described before, in this specific case, the ‘native conditions without anthropogenic land use’ is replaced by the concept of ‘semi-natural reference’ represented by grasslands. Concerning the indicators, we believe that single indicators can give a limited lens and may underestimate the level of debt, whereas our combined approach reveals a broader lens for LD through global change, in particular, identifying hot-spots for the different kinds of LD. Therefore, for this protocol we defined 10 indicators of LD processes, which are listed in Table 1 and described below.

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of the LMI_{debt}

Table 1. The land degradation indicators considered for assessing the land multi-degradation in olive orchards.

No	LD processes	Examples of negative effects on agricultural land productivity.	Units	Reference
1	Cumulative erosion rate	Degrading soil structure, reducing soil depth, decreasing/losing the soil nutrient content, accelerating dust emission, damaging plants by abrasion, among others.	t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	Panagos, et al. (2015) Montgomery (2007).
2	Gully erosion and badlands	Heavily degraded landscape, reducing soil depth, decreasing/losing the soil nutrient content, alter subsoil hydrology, reduced farmable land, among others.	% of area	Poesen et al. (2003)
3	Soil organic matter	Disrupting structural stability and water holding capacity of soils, decreasing soil fertility, among others.	g per kg	Lal (2018) Fu et al. (2021)
4	Status of ground vegetation	Decreasing soil organic carbon via lower input to soil or through increased land exposure to water and wind erosion, among others.	%	Panagos et al (2015) Ledo et al. (2020)

5	Soil salinity	Limiting plant growth due to phytotoxicity, water uptake difficulty, or soil organic carbon losses, among others, among others.	%	Minhas et al. (2020) Corwin et al. (2021)
6	Soil acidification	Threats to soil biology, change in plant communities, increasing availability and toxicity of pollutants for plants and soil biota, or limiting soil nutrient availability, among others.	pH units	FAO (2015) Zang (2015)
7	Soil compaction	Reducing soil porosity, shrinking oxygen and water supply to plants, or restricting root penetration, among others.	kg/sq cm	Shah et al. (2017) Stoessel et al. (2018)
8	Soil nutrient imbalances	Amplifying acidity and micronutrient deficiencies in soils, due to N or P excess, or limiting plant growth, due to N or P deficit.	mg/kg (P)	Gregory et al. (2017) Panagos et al. (2022b)
9	Soil pollution from heavy metals	Poisoning the soil, injuring plants via chlorosis and necrosis, or hindering root growth and crop yields, among others.	mg/kg	Nagajyoti, et al. (2010)
10	Soil moisture	Soil moisture affects soil formation, structure, stability and erosion and is of primary concern with respect to plant growth and soil biology, among others.	%	Právělie (2016)

4.2.1 Cumulative soil erosion rates [CSE]

Soil erosion is the removal of soil by wind, water, and other processes. The cumulative erosion rate in olive groves can be approximatively assessed as the sum of cumulative soil erosion rates estimated with the following spatially distributed techniques: Water (Panagos, Borrelli, Poesen, et al., 2015), wind (Borrelli, Robinson, Fleischer et al. 2017), and tillage (Van Oost, Cerdan, and Quine 2009) (note that gully erosion and general desertification as badlands is considered separately). The lower soil tolerance limit for non-degraded (healthy) soils was set to 2 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, in line with the threshold reported in the draft of the Soil Monitoring Law (COM(2023)416).

Table 2. Cumulative erosion rates of water, wind, tillage, and harvest erosion.

Cumulative erosion rates of water, wind, and tillage (t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Scores
Cumulative erosion rate < 2 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	0
Cumulative erosion rate 2 - 5 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	1
Cumulative erosion rate 5 - 10 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	2
Cumulative erosion rate > 10 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	3

4.2.2. Farmable land loss due to gully erosion and badlands [G&B]

According to Poesen (2018) gully erosion can be one of the most severe forms of erosion, with gullies locally accounting for up to 80% of the total soil displacement due to water erosion. Although difficult to quantitatively assess through spatial prediction modelling, the observation in field as well as the remote on-screen mapping of gully erosion features is quite straightforward. With regard to badlands, these are represented by extensive tracts of heavily eroded land which result uncultivable. Their field and on-screen mapping is also straightforward. Occurrence of gullies and badlands result on loss of farmable surface. The lower number of tolerance limit for non-degraded (healthy) soils concerning gully erosion and badlands was set to 0%.

Table 3. Area prone to gully erosion and badlands

Area interested by gully erosion and badlands (%)	Scores
Portion of field interested by gully/badlands: 0%	0
Portion of field interested by gully/badlands: 0 - 15%	1
Portion of field interested by gully/badlands: 16 - 30%	2
Portion of field interested by gully/badlands: > 30%	3

4.2.3. Soil organic matter [SOM]

Topsoil (0-20cm) organic matter is the organic matter component of soil that is made up of plant and animal detritus at various stages of decomposition, soil microbe cells and tissues, and compounds that soil microbes produce. SOM is a vital component of soil fertility and its decrease in mineral soils diminishes the ability to cycle nutrients and water and, in turn, to sustain soil biodiversity. SOM concentrations in mineral soils typically range between 1% and 6% of the total mass of topsoil in most highland soils. Topsoil containing less than 1% organic matter are typically found in deserts. The lower soil tolerance limit for non-degraded (healthy) soils was set to 2.5% SOM content (Dogan and Gülser, 2020; Palese et al., 2014; IOC, 2007; USDA, 1998). It should be added that this limit only holds true for soils under agricultural use, e.g. arable soils or managed grasslands, as there are, of course, natural soils with low carbon content which are still healthy (e.g., sandy young dunes, young soils under glacial retreat etc.).

Table 4. Soil Organic Matter.

SOM concentration (%)	Scores
SOM > 2.5%	0
SOM 2 - 2.5%	1
SOM 1 - 2%	2
SOM < 1%	3

4.2.4. Status of ground vegetation [SGV]

The existence, longevity, and density of ground vegetation cover, as well as its net primary productivity, are critical for soil health, as they provide energy and nutrients for soil biodiversity, carbon inputs to soil organic matter, and reduce erosion and surface runoff. A long-lasting

ground vegetation cover suggests good conditions for soil biodiversity and soil health in general. In addition, it reduces the impact of raindrops and wind, which can induce particle detachment. Green vegetation and/or plant residue increase surface roughness, help to retain water in small hollows and sinks formed by residue buildup, increase infiltration rates due to root channels and thus decreasing and slowing surface runoff. In warm climates, vegetation cover further regulates the heat stress experienced by the soil. The lower soil tolerance limit for non-degraded (healthy) soils was set to 80% of ground cover.

Table 5. Permanent (winter and spring) ground vegetation cover.

Permanent ground vegetation cover (%)	Scores
Herbaceous vegetation covering > 80%	0
Herbaceous vegetation covering 60 - 80%	1
Herbaceous vegetation covering 40 - 60%	2
Herbaceous vegetation covering < 40%	3

4.2.5. Soil salinity [SSa]

Topsoil (0-20cm) salinity indicates the presence of excess soluble salts which hinder crop water absorption and may cause toxicity problems. It is measured in terms of the electrical conductivity in a saturated extract (EC_e). A soil is defined as being saline when EC_e > 4 dS/m (Hassani et al., 2020). The olive tree is considered to be moderately tolerant to salinity and it can stand a higher content of salts than other fruit tree species (IOC, 2007). However, the lower soil tolerance limit for non-degraded (healthy) soils for salinity was set to EC_e > 2.8 dS m⁻¹ (modified after Dogan and Gülser (2020) and IOC (2007)).

Table 6. Soil salinization scores.

Salinization based on electrical conductivity (ECs in dS m ⁻¹)	Scores
Electrical conductivity < 2.8 dS m ⁻¹	0
Electrical conductivity 2.8 - 4 dS m ⁻¹	1
Electrical conductivity 4 - 6 dS m ⁻¹	2
Electrical conductivity > 6 dS m ⁻¹	3

4.2.6. Soil acidification [SAC]

Topsoil (0-20cm) acidification is caused by the accumulation of soluble inorganic and organic acids, at a faster rate than they can be neutralized. It decreases soil pH over time and may result in reduced soil fertility and loss of soil biodiversity, and, while one of the chemical properties of olive is that it adapts to different pH values, the lower soil tolerance limit for non-degraded (healthy) soils was set to 6.8-7.3.

Table 7. Soil acidification.

Soil acidification based on pH	Scores
pH > 6.8-7.3	0
pH 6.0-6.8 or 7.3-8.0	1
pH 6.0-5.0 or 8.0-8.5	2

Soil acidification based on pH	Scores
pH > 6.8-7.3	0
pH 6.0-6.8 or 7.3-8.0	1
pH < 5.0 or > 8.5	3

4.2.7. Soil compaction [SCo]

Topsoil (0-20cm) compaction is the reduction of microcavities or pores in the soil. Soil compaction is often permanent or takes a long time to correct, especially in the deeper parts of the soil that machinery cannot reach (subsoil compaction). Compaction is most severe when pressure is applied under wet conditions and the soil is softer, losing more volume for a given pressure. These limit infiltration and can cause subsurface waterlogging, so encouraging erosion and the loss of SOC and nutrients. The lower soil tolerance limit for non-degraded (healthy) soils was set to 1.2 g cm³. (after Panagos et al., 2014; Doğan and Gülser, 2020)

Table 8. Degree of soil compaction.

Bulk density (BD) in topsoil (g cm ⁻³)	Scores
BD in topsoil < 1.2 g cm ³	0
BD in topsoil 1.2 - 1.4 g cm ³	1
BD in topsoil 1.41 - 1.6 g cm ³	2
BD in topsoil > 1.6 g cm ³	3

4.2.8. Phosphorus deficiency [Pdf]

Topsoil (0-20cm) phosphorus is a condition associated with insufficient supply of phosphorus (P, in mg/kg) which is likely to decrease in land productivity). P is important for fertilizing annual crops, but less important in perennial and woody crops because of the ease with which they re-use this element and the low amounts removed. Based on the EUSO and other literature (Doğan and Gülser, 2020; USDA, 1998) an initial deficit condition was set to when P level is <50 mg/kg.

Table 9. Soil nutrient imbalances.

Phosphorus concentration (mg/kg)	Scores
Phosphorus concentration 50 - 20 mg/kg	0
Phosphorus concentration 20 - 10 mg/kg	1
Phosphorus concentration 10 - 5 mg/kg	2
Phosphorus concentration < 5 mg/kg	3

4.2.9. Soil pollution from heavy metals [SHM]

The assessment of topsoil (0-20cm) heavy metal contaminations is based on the European Council directive on the preservation of the environment, particularly the soil, when sewage sludge is utilized in agriculture (EC Directive 68|278|EEC, June 12, 1986). Following this directive, the limit of the four deducting scores is established according to the average value of the limit specified in the directive considering: copper, mercury, zinc, cadmium, nickel, and lead (after SHERPA, Alewell et al. in progress).

Table 10. Limit concentrations of heavy metals in topsoil.

Copper (mg/kg)	Mercury (µg/kg)	Zinc (mg/kg)	Cadmium (mg/kg)	Nickel (mg/kg)	Lead (mg/kg)	Scores
< 23	< 26	< 33	< 0.4	< 8.5	< 23	0
23 - 50	26 - 485	33 - 105	0.4 - 1	8.5 - 25	23 - 80	1
50 - 77	485 - 944	105 - 177	1 - 1.6	25 - 41.5	80 - 137	2
> 95	> 1250	> 225	> 2	> 52.5	> 175	3

4.2.10. Soil moisture [SMo]

Annual average topsoil moisture is the water stored in unsaturated soils. It is an environmental variable that combines the influence of climate, topography, soil characteristic, plants, and human management, and therefore extremely relevant in the case of water-limited ecosystems. Soil moisture measurement can be based on in situ probes (e.g., capacitance probes, neutron probes) and proximal (UAV drones) or remote (satellites) sensing methods. A higher diversity of insects is correlated with increased soil moisture. For instance, soil moisture content is a major governing factor in a grassland ecosystem that influences prokaryotic community diversity. The lower soil tolerance limit for non-degraded (healthy) soils was set to 85%.

Table 11. Total amount of water in soil.

Estimated topsoil moisture (%)	Scores
Estimated topsoil moisture >85%	0
Estimated topsoil moisture 0.72 - 0.85%	1
Estimated topsoil moisture 0.65 – 0.45%	2
Estimated topsoil moisture <0.45%	3

4.3 Example of the Land Multidegradation Index LMI_{debt}

At the current stage, with the laboratory work on the soil samples collected across 53 SOIL OLIVE's olive orchard sites has recently been completed, and while the Soil Districts framework is still in conceptualization at the EU level, we report, by way of example, the results of the testing of the Land Multidegradation Index for two target olive orchard sites (LMI_{target}). The two olive orchards are located in Spain (left) and Italy (right), but the exact locations are not disclosed for privacy reasons. Both sites were part of the LUCAS 2009 Topsoil Survey, which included, among other soil properties, also the heavy metals content. Accordingly, all required soil information could be retrieved from LUCAS soil properties, while for the other indicators the required information was acquired via ad hoc modelling, on-screen interpretation of multitemporal imagery, and Copernicus' earth observation data. The 'semi-natural reference' LMI_{base}) for this example was set to a hypothetical value of 4. As illustrated in Fig. 4, the LMI_{debt} values for each olive orchard are then computed through arithmetic difference.

LUCAS point olive orchard Spain					
No	LD	0	1	2	3
1	CSE				
2	G&B				
3	SOM				
4	SGV				
5	SSa				
6	SAC				
7	SCo				
8	PDf				
9	SHM				
10	SMo				
<i>LMI_{target}</i>		14			
Assumed <i>LMI_{base}</i> of the Soil District		4			
<i>LMI_{debt}</i>		4 – 14 = -10			

LUCAS point olive orchard Italy					
No	LD	0	1	2	3
1	CSE				
2	G&B				
3	SOM				
4	SGV				
5	SSa				
6	SAC				
7	SCo				
8	PDf				
9	SHM				
10	SMo				
<i>LMI_{target}</i>		12			
Assumed <i>LMI_{base}</i> of the Soil District		4			
<i>LMI_{debt}</i>		4 – 12 = -8			

Figure 4. Example of LMI_{debt} computation for two target sites in Spain (left) and Italy (right).

4.4 Future testing sites

The study sites that will be used for future testing and implementation of the designed methodology include 53 olive orchard fields distributed across four pan-Mediterranean countries, i.e., Greece, Italy, Marocco, Portugal, and Spain (Table 1). The total land surface is ca. 2,200 hectares (ha). The distribution of the sites is illustrated in Figure 4.

Table 12. Olive orchard plots with size (ha) and type of management (DH, ORG, and TD).

SPAIN		GREECE		MAROCCO		ITALY		PORTUGAL	
ID	ha	ID	ha	ID	ha	ID	ha	ID	ha
ES-HD10	0.0069	GR-HD43	1.1	IT-ORG17	0.6	MR-ORG23	38.5	PT-HD51	58.7
ES-HD2	16.5	GR-ORG32	1.0	IT-ORG18	10.4	MR-TD24	7.9	PT-HD52	676.8
ES-HD22	21.7	GR-ORG33	1.3	IT-ORG19	11.7	MR-TD25	40.6	PT-HD53	402.8
ES-HD3	171.6	GR-ORG34	0.6	IT-ORG48	6.8	MR-TD26	58.6	PT-TD41	2.1
ES-HD40	10.4	GR-ORG38	11.5	IT-ORG49	17.0	MR-TD27	2.3	PT-TD42	5.8
ES-HD8	104.3	GR-ORG39	1.6	IT-TD16	0.5	MR-TD28	7.1		
ES-ORG11	19.9	GR-ORG45	2.1	IT-TD20	1.5	MR-TD29	12.7		
ES-ORG12	3.0	GR-ORG47	0.5	IT-TD21	11.4				
ES-ORG13	17.1	GR-TD30	1.3	IT-TD50	1.7				
ES-ORG14	46.0	GR-TD31	1.2						
ES-ORG4	380.3	GR-TD35	0.5						
ES-ORG6	3.4	GR-TD36	1.2						
ES-TD1	102.0	GR-TD37	0.2						
ES-TD15	5.3	GR-TD44	0.3						
ES-TD5	7.8	GR-TD46	1.4						
ES-TD7	1.1								
ES-TD9	49.1								

Figure 5. Spatial distribution of the SOIL O-LIVE orchard plots across the Mediterranean region.

5. Conclusions

The United Nations (UN) General Assembly resolution A/RES/73/284 proclaimed 2021–2030 the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration, which has the aim to “prevent, halt and reverse the degradation of ecosystems worldwide”. The SDGs as part of the 2030 UN agenda provide a roadmap for a sustainable world including 17 goals that are addressed with subsequent targets. ‘Land Degradation Neutrality’ (target 15.3) aims to achieve LD neutrality by 2030. In this context, the European Commission has proposed the Soil Strategy for 2030, which together with the Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience targets to grant soils the same level of protection in the EU as water and air.

In this protocol, our approach built on the previous experiences of Panagos, Borrelli, Jones et al. (2024) and Právělie, Borrelli, Panagos et al. (2024) to develop a methodology to best serve LD assessment in olive orchard sites. The proposed methodology allows the assessment of the degree of LD of a specific olive orchard quantitatively and objectively. This can be done in both absolute and relative terms. In absolute terms, LMI_{target} enables the comparison of the scores obtained in targeted olive orchard with any other orchard across the Mediterranean area and beyond. This is done without taking into account the original pedoclimatic condition of the site. By contrast, the LMI_{debt} resulting from the comparison of LMI_{base} with LMI_{target} , which represent the ‘semi-natural reference’ of a given Soil District, provides a relative assessment of LD able to account for the starting soil condition of a given pedoclimatic environment.

The assessment of the proposed LMI in the experimental sites of SOIL O-LIVE will ultimately enable the possibility to analyse the impact of multi LD processes on soils from olive groves in terms of multi-biodiversity and ecological functions at different levels of organization and scales. In addition, by interacting with the stakeholder of this interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary consortium it will be possible to (i) investigate the relationship of soil health status with quality and safety of olive soil, (ii) design the implementation of effective soil amendments and ecological restoration practices, and (iii) contribute to the development of explicit norms and regulations to design novel future certifications for healthy soils in European olive oil.

References

- 1.Barbier, E. B., & Hochard, J. P. (2018). Land degradation and poverty. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(11), 623-631.
- 2.Borrelli, P., Panagos, P., Alewell, C., Ballabio, C., de Oliveira Fagundes, H., Haregeweyn, N., ... & Robinson, D. A. (2023). Policy implications of multiple concurrent soil erosion processes in European farmland. *Nature Sustainability*, 6(1), 103-112.
- 3.Cherlet, M., Hutchinson, C., Reynolds, J., Hill, J., Sommer, S., & Von Maltitz, G. *World Atlas of Desertification*; Publications Office of the European Union: Luxembourg, 2018.
- 4.Corwin, D. L. (2021). Climate change impacts on soil salinity in agricultural areas. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 72(2), 842-862.
- 5.De Rosa, D., Ballabio, C., Lugato, E., Fasiolo, M., Jones, A., & Panagos, P. (2024). Soil organic carbon stocks in European croplands and grasslands: How much have we lost in the past decade?. *Global Change Biology*, 30(1), e16992.
- 6.Doğan, B., & Gülser, C. (2020). Soil quality assessment for olive groves areas of Menderes District, Izmir-Turkey. *Eurasian Journal of Soil Science*, 9(4), 298-305.
- 7.EEA, 2000 *Down to Earth: Soil Degradation and Sustainable Development in Europe: a Challenge for the 21st Century* European Environment Agency, 2000 - Environmental policy
- 8.ELD Initiative 2015. *The Economics of Land Degradation. The value of land: Prosperous lands and positive rewards through sustainable land management* (Bonn, Germany).
- 9.FAO, UNEP and UNESCO, "A Provisional Methodology for Soil Degradation Assessment," FAO, Rome, 1979.
- 10.FAO, 1999. *Poverty alleviation and food security in Asia*. In: *Land degradation*, Chapter 3. Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO) (URL: https://www.fao.org/3/x6625e/x6625e02b.htm#P358_65507).
- 11.FAO – *Status of the world’s soil resources – Main report* (UN Food and Agriculture Organization, Rome, Italy, 2015).
- 12.Fu, Z., Hu, W., Beare, M., Thomas, S., Carrick, S., Dando, J., ... & Lilburne, L. (2021). Land use effects on soil hydraulic properties and the contribution of soil organic carbon. *Journal of Hydrology*, 602, 126741.
- 13.Gregory, P. J., Wahbi, A., Adu-Gyamfi, J., Heiling, M., Gruber, R., Joy, E. J., & Broadley, M. R. (2017). Approaches to reduce zinc and iron deficits in food systems. *Global Food Security*, 15, 1-10. Gregory, P. J. et al. Approaches to reduce zinc and iron deficits in food systems. *Glob. Food Sec.* 15, 1–10 (2017).
- 14.IOC, 2007. *Production Techniques in Olive Growing*. Sbitri, M.O, Serafini, F.(Eds.), International Olive Council, Madrid-Spain.
- 15.Lal, R. (2018). Digging deeper: A holistic perspective of factors affecting soil organic carbon sequestration in agroecosystems. *Global change biology*, 24(8), 3285-3301.

16. Ledo, A., Smith, P., Zerihun, A., Whitaker, J., Vicente-Vicente, J. L., Qin, Z., ... & Hillier, J. (2020). Changes in soil organic carbon under perennial crops. *Glo cha bio*, 26, 4158-4168.
17. Minhas, P. S., Ramos, T. B., Ben-Gal, A., & Pereira, L. S. (2020). Coping with salinity in irrigated agriculture: Crop evapotranspiration and water management issues. *Agricultural Water Management*, 227, 105832.
18. Montanarella, L., Scholes, R., & Brainich, A. (2018). The assessment report on land degradation and restoration. Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES): Bonn, Germany.
19. Montgomery, D. R. (2007). Soil erosion and agricultural sustainability. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(33), 13268-13272.
20. Nagajyoti, P. C., Lee, K. D. & Sreekanth, T. V. Heavy metals, occurrence and toxicity for plants: a review. *Environ. Chem. Lett.* 8, 199–216 (2010).
21. Oldeman, L. Soil Resilience and Sustainable Land Use, 19–36 (ISRIC, Wageningen, 1994).
22. Olsson, L. et al. (2019). Land degradation (Climate Change and Land: An IPCC Special Report on Climate Change, Desertification, Land Degradation, Sustainable Land Management, Food Security, and Greenhouse Gas Fluxes in Terrestrial Ecosystems in press.
23. Palese, A. M., Vignozzi, N., Celano, G., Agnelli, A. E., Pagliai, M., & Xiloyannis, C. (2014). Influence of soil management on soil physical characteristics and water storage in a mature rainfed olive orchard. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 144, 96-109.
24. Panagos et al. "The new assessment of soil loss by water erosion in Europe [J]." *Environmental Science & Policy* 8 (2015): 438-447.
25. Panagos, P., Van Liedekerke, M., Borrelli, P., Köninger, J., Ballabio, C., Orgiazzi, A., ... & Montanarella, L. (2022a). European Soil Data Centre 2.0: Soil data and knowledge in support of the EU policies. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 73(6), e13315.
26. Panagos, P. et al. (2022b) Improving the phosphorus budget of European agricultural soils. *Sci. Total Environ.* 853, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158706>.
27. Panagos, P., Borrelli, P., Jones, A., & Robinson, D. A. (2024). A 1 billion euro mission: A Soil Deal for Europe. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 75(1), e13466.
28. Panagos, P., De Rosa, D., Liakos, L., Labouyrie, M., Borrelli, P., & Ballabio, C. (2024). Soil bulk density assessment in Europe. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 364, 108907.
29. Poesen, J., Nachtergaele, J., Verstraeten, G., & Valentin, C. (2003). Gully erosion and environmental change: importance and research needs. *Catena*, 50(2-4), 91-133.
30. Poesen, J. (2018). Soil erosion in the Anthropocene: Research needs. *Earth surface processes and landforms*, 43(1), 64-84.
31. Právělie, R. (2016). Drylands extent and environmental issues. A global approach. *Earth Sci. Rev.* 161, 259–278,.

32. Právělie, R. (2021). Exploring the multiple land degradation pathways across the planet. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 220, 103689.
33. Právělie, R., Borrelli, P., Panagos, P., Ballabio, C., Lugato, E., Chappell, A., ... & Birsan, M. V. (2024). A unifying modelling of multiple land degradation pathways in Europe. *Nature Communications*, 15(1), 3862.
34. Shah, A. N. et al. Soil compaction effects on soil health and crop productivity: An overview. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 24, 10056–10067 (2017)
35. Stoessel, F., Sonderegger, T., Bayer, P. & Hellweg, S. (2018). Assessing the environmental impacts of soil compaction in Life Cycle Assessment. *Sci. Total Environ.* 630, 913–921 (2018).
36. UNCCD – Global land outlook, First edition (United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification, UNCCD secretariat, Bonn, Germany, 2017).
37. USDA 1998. Soil quality test kit guide. Soil Quality Institute, National Resources Conservation Service, United States Department of Agriculture.
38. Van Oost, K., Cerdan, O., & Quine, T. A. (2009). Accelerated sediment fluxes by water and tillage erosion on European agricultural land. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 34(12), 1625-1634.
39. Zhang, X., Liu, W., Zhang, G., Jiang, L. & Han, X. (2015) Mechanisms of soil acidification reducing bacterial diversity. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 81, 275–281.